

The stability constants of the trivalent rare earth metal ions follow the order : $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} < \text{Nd}^{\text{III}} < \text{Sm}^{\text{III}} > \text{Gd}^{\text{III}}$.

Such difference in the trend of stability constants is not uncommon in the case of lanthanides¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and this may be traced to be due to the varying degree of stabilizations arising out of interactions of 4f metal orbitals with the ligand field²⁰.

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Kinetics of Discharge of Zinc(II) and Nickel(II) Ions at the D.M.E. in Dithiodipropionic Acid

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THE electrochemical behaviour of several mercapto compounds and their metal complexes has already been studied¹⁻⁶ in these laboratories and yielded useful results. This communication reports the polarographic reduction of zinc and nickel in presence of dithiodipropionic acid, the determination of kinetic parameters under various experimental conditions and the values of change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for

the electrode reactions. The literature is, however, silent on these investigations.

Experimental

Dithiodipropionic acid (DTDPA) of 99% purity was supplied by Evan's Chemetics, New York. Zinc and nickel contents of zinc sulphate and nickel sulphate solutions were checked by estimating them as zinc pyrophosphate and nickel dimethylglyoximate. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Thymol was used as a maximum suppressor at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 1 M$) maintained by NaClO_4 .

C-V curves were drawn on a manual polarograph in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen using S.C.E. as the reference electrode with a thermostated H-cell. The capillary had the following characteristics: $m = 1.862 \text{ mg sec}^{-1}$, $t = 3.66 \text{ sec}$, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.878 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$ at $h_{Hg} = 50 \text{ cms}$.

The current was recorded at the end of the drop-life instead of average current because the determination of kinetic parameters is based on Koutecky's method more accurately reproduced by measuring the maximum current⁶.

Results and Discussion

The conventional log plots of the reduction waves of Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} in dithiodipropionic acid were straight lines but their slopes were not agreeing with the theoretical values indicating the irreversible nature of the waves in both the systems.

Effect of pH: Polarograms of 1 mM Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} in 0.04 M DTDPA and 1 M NaClO_4 were recorded in the pH range 1-7. It was observed that below pH 3.5 and above pH 5.5, the waves were not regular. However, a very well defined single cathodic wave was obtained at pH 4 where subsequent studies were carried out in both cases.

The values of half wave potentials in the case of Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} at pH 4 were -1.006 and -0.84, respectively. An examination of polarographic waves revealed that with increase in pH, the $-E_{1/2}$ displaced towards more negative potential showing the complex formation between $\text{Zn}^{2+}/\text{Ni}^{2+}$ with DTDPA.

Effect of Hg pressure and temperature: The plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} (uncorrected) and temperature were found to be linear both in case of Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} .

The constancy of $i_d/h^{1/2}$ in each case and the values of temperature coefficients of i_d indicated the diffusion controlled nature of the waves.

Solutions of 0.04 M DTDPA and 1 mM Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} polarographed at temperatures 25, 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50° showed that the $E_{1/2}$ shifted to more positive values with the increase in temperature

TABLE 1—VALUES OF i_d , $E_{1/2}$, αn AND $k_{f,h}^0$ AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF DTDPA FOR 1m M Zn^{2+} AND Ni^{2+} SYSTEMS AT 80°

Concn. M	i_d (μA)		$-E_{1/2}$ V		αn		$k_{f,h}^0$ cm/sec ⁻¹	
	Zn^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	$Zn^{2+} \times 10^{-17}$	$Ni^{2+} \times 10^{-7}$
0.02	16.23	14.52	1.002	0.837	1.355	0.615	0.051	0.770
0.04	15.48	13.96	1.006	0.84	1.290	0.553	0.136	1.49
0.06	14.92	13.39	1.009	0.844	1.231	0.483	0.443	4.49
0.08	14.38	12.92	1.011	0.848	1.178	0.455	1.42	5.82
0.10	13.47	12.35	1.013	0.853	1.129	0.430	4.24	7.43
0.12	12.98	11.98	1.015	0.858	1.084	0.410	12.10	8.71

TABLE 2—VALUES OF i_d , $E_{1/2}$, αn AND $k_{f,h}^0$ AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES FOR 1m M Zn^{2+} AND Ni^{2+} SYSTEMS AT 0.04 M [DTDPA]

Temp. °C	i_d μA		$-E_{1/2}$ V		αn		$k_{f,h}^0$ cm sec ⁻¹	
	Zn^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	$Zn^{2+} \times 10^{-16}$	$Ni^{2+} \times 10^{-6}$
25	14.34	13.3	1.008	0.844	1.062	0.437	10.40	2.05
30	15.48	13.96	1.006	0.84	1.106	0.444	3.29	1.85
35	16.22	14.71	1.008	0.836	1.153	0.451	0.973	1.81
40	16.98	15.47	1.001	0.831	1.178	0.468	0.532	1.58
45	17.73	16.41	0.996	0.826	1.231	0.475	0.147	1.39
50	18.68	17.17	0.990	0.821	1.290	0.488	0.037	1.20

(Table 1) showing the easier reduction of the complexes at elevated temperatures which is in accordance with the irreversible nature of the electrode process⁷⁻⁸.

Effect of concentration of DTDPA: Polarograms of solutions containing different concentrations of DTDPA (0.02-0.12 M) and 1 mM Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} showed that with the increase in [DTDPA], the $E_{1/2}$ is displaced towards more negative potential and i_d decreases in each case indicating the complex formation between metal ion and DTDPA (Table 1).

Nature of complex: Since the polarographic waves were irreversible in both Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions, the classical method of Lingane⁹ could not be used for studying the complex ion formation. Therefore, the method recommended by Tamamushi and Tanaka¹⁰ was employed, using the following equation.

$$\frac{\Delta E_{1/2}}{\Delta \log C_X} = -q \frac{0.06014}{n\alpha}$$

Where α is the fraction of the total applied potential that favours the forward reaction and q is the number of ligands bound to the metal. The value of $n\alpha$ is obtained from the equation

$$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4} = \frac{-0.0574}{n\alpha}$$

The value of $\Delta E_{1/2}/\Delta \log C_X$ is determined from the slope of plots of $\log C_X$ vs $E_{1/2}$, where C_X is the concentration of the DTDPA. The value of q thus obtained works out to be approximately 1 in both the cases showing thereby that one mole of

DTDPA combines with one mole of metal ion suggesting the formation of 1 : 1 complex between Zn^{2+}/Ni^{2+} and DTDPA.

Kinetic parameters: Since zinc and nickel reduce irreversibly at D.M.E. in presence of DTDPA, the values of transfer coefficient (α) and formal rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) for the electrode reactions have been determined under various conditions by Koutecky's method¹¹ as extended by Meites and Israel¹² using the following standard equations.

$$E_{a.o.} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \quad (1)$$

where

$$E_{1/2} = -0.2412 + \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 k_{f,h}^0 t^{1/2}}{D_o^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

The values of αn was obtained by equating the slope of $E_{a.o.}$ vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$ plot to $-0.0542/\alpha n$ and the intercept of the same plot ($E_{1/2}$) was used to calculate $k_{f,h}^0$. The values of $D_o^{1/2}$ were determined from Ilkovic equation. The values of αn and different temperatures are summarised in Table 1 and 2.

Thermodynamic parameters: The enthalpy of activation (ΔH) for the electrode reaction has been calculated by equating the slope of $\log k_{f,h}^0$ vs $1/T$ plot to $-\Delta H/2.303R$ and found to be -31.89 and -2.080 kcal mol⁻¹ for zinc and nickel systems, respectively.

The free energy of activation (ΔG) can be determined by expliciting the value of $k_{f,h}^0$ on the basis of general principles of the absolute rate theory